

INVESTIGATING THE EFFECT OF TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP ON EMPLOYEES' COMMUNICATIONAL PERFORMANCE

INVESTIGACIÓN DEL EFECTO DEL LIDERAZGO TRANSFORMACIONAL EN EL DESEMPEÑO COMUNICACIONAL DE EMPLEADOS

Nader Bohlooli Zeinab ¹ bohlooli@yahoo.com	Hojjat Montazer Khorasan ² manager139071@gmail.com	Fariba Adel Eskandani ³ faribaadel68@gmail.com

Resumen

En esta investigación, la relación entre las cuatro dimensiones del estilo de liderazgo transformacional, que incluye la influencia ideacional, la motivación inspiradora, la persuasión subjetiva y las consideraciones individuales, se ha analizado con el desempeño comunicacional del personal. Los resultados de la prueba de correlación de Pearson mostraron que existe una relación significativa entre el liderazgo transformacional y el rendimiento comunicativo. Además, investigar la relación entre las dimensiones del liderazgo transformacional y el desempeño comunicativo mostró que la consideración individual y la persuasión mental están correlacionadas con el desempeño comunicativo.

Palabras clave: Estimulación intelectual, consideración individualizada, liderazgo transformacional, función comunicativa.

Abstract

In this research, the relationship between the four dimensions of the transformational leadership style, which includes ideational influence, inspirational motivation, subjective persuasion and individual considerations, has been analyzed with the communicational performance of the staff. The results of Pearson correlation test showed that there is a meaningful relationship between Transformational leadership and communicational performance. Also, Investigate the relationship between dimensions of transformational leadership and communicational performance showed that individual consideration and mental persuasion are correlated with communicational performance.

Keywords: intellectual stimulation, Individualized consideration, transformational leadership, communicative function.

DOI:<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7800157>

1 Assistant professor of management, Bonab Branch, Islamic Azad University, Bonab, Iran

2 PhD student of management, Bonab Branch, Islamic Azad University, Bonab, Iran

3 Assistant professor of management, Bonab Branch, Islamic Azad University, Bonab, Iran

INTRODUCTION

Today, successful organizations have the ability to predict environmental changes and can provide the necessary mechanisms to coordinate with these changes. However, it is important to note that implementation of the transformation simply does not happen. An organizational change for many employees is a stressful experience because the change may be uncertain and affects the feelings and abilities of employees. Therefore, employees usually do not support change, unless they want it out of it and get excited for it (Nordin, 2011, 131). In this modern era where world has become a global village, firms are considered to be competitive on the basis of competence of their human resources. It is somewhat a difficult task to handle people who are physically, psychologically, culturally and ethnically different from each other. Management of employees is largely dependent on the quality of leadership organizations have (Albion, Gagliardi, 2007).

Given that influence in organizations is considered a fundamental route to promote alignment of corporate strategic goals and the actions of those striving to achieve them, the talent to convert employees into engaged agents has long been viewed as one of the skills essential to highly effective organizational leaders (Teal, 1998, 150). Transformational Leadership Theory has been proposed with this focus (Lowe, Gardner, 2000, 467) and has undergirded a number of scientific studies, becoming a leading stream of inquiry in the international literature (Antonakis, 2012; Gardner, Lowe, Moss, Mahoney, Cogliser, 2010).

Because the stable transformation in organizations depends on its acceptance by employees (Zahedi, Mortazavi, 2010, 125) and does not change unless One is ready for it (Legzian, Malekzadeh, 2010, 104). Therefore, successful organizational change depends on the ability of leaders to recognize the need for change and planning in order to achieve that management, along with the workforce, with unity and integrity. Achievement of the goals set beforehand (Mirkamali, Zahedi, 2012, 37). Therefore, successful organizations need transformational leaders who need to be proficient in defining the proper direction and direction of the organization, directing people to that direction, and motivating the transformation of employees (Mazlomi et al., 2013, 36).

Leadership continued to be one of the most widely discussed topics by the researchers from all over the world. Jong and Hartog (2007) described leadership as a process to influence people in order to get desired results. Lok and Crawford (2004) proclaimed that leadership plays a vital role in determining the success and failure of a firm. Gill (2006) identified that leaders help to stimulate, motivate, encourage, and recognize their followers in order to get key performance results (Bushra and et.all.2011, 261). Because transformational leaders provide constructive feedback to their followers, encourage them to think creatively about problems, and show the ability to convince them to exert effort, their subordinates should generally benefit from such influence and more easily achieve higher levels of formal performance (Cavazotte, 2013,493)

LITERATURE REVIEW

TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP

Transformational leadership moves beyond a simple exchange process. They create challenges and expectations as well as allowing other people to achieve higher levels of performance. Transformational leader believed to be able to bring better change and can improve performance of his employees. On transformational leadership, subordinates feel trust, admire and respect the leadership, loyal, and willing to work hard for the company (in Timothy Bass, 2011, 102). Bass (2005) says that Transformational leadership directs the attention of followers to collective goals and encourages them to pursue organizational goals to stimulate high-level motivation. Literature reviews and studies accumulated in recent years on transformational leadership show its positive association with performance outcomes (Avolio, 1999; Avolio, Bass, & Jung, 1995; Lowe et al., 1996), particularly in private companies (Dumdum, Lowe, Avolio, 2002, 40).

Similarly, meta-analyses covering empirical studies indicate that there is a strong connection between transformational leadership and subordinates' formal task performance and contextual performance; i.e., undertaking actions that go beyond formal roles, but that also contribute to the good functioning of the company (Judge, Piccolo, 2004, 758). The charismatic-transformational approach to leadership has developed based on two seminal perspectives, Max Weber's Theory of Charisma (1947) and Burns' (1978) Transforming Leadership Theory. Bass (1985) coined the term transformational leadership, describing such leaders as change agents that elicit and transform followers' beliefs, attitudes and motivations. These leaders provide a vision and develop an emotional relationship with their followers, increasing the latter's consciousness and belief in higher goals, above their own interests (Nezhad & Jenaabadi, 2014; Amin & Mariani, 2017).

Bass and Avolio (1994) suggest four essential scopes of transformational leadership theory, this include: *intellectual stimulation*, *inspirational motivation*, *individualized consideration* and *idealized influence*. Idealized influence is exhibited when followers respect and trust their leaders and want to be like them, also the leader tends to put his/her followers' needs over their own. Inspirational motivation is when a leader acts in a way that causes people around him/her to be motivated to work better, usually caused by the leader instilling a sense of meaning in the work for the follower. Individualized consideration is shown when a leader gives attention to each employee and is concerned with his/her individual needs; also, the leader is generally seen as a coach or a mentor. Intellectual stimulation is demonstrated when a leader asks questions to try and increase productivity and innovation (Avolio, Bass, 2004)

COMMUNICATIONAL PERFORMANCE

Communication is the primary element of the management profession. Managers should communicate with people at different levels. The relationship of the manager with those who work for him may be the most important

communication, because aspects of work such as training, mission referral and performance evaluation are done through communication. Therefore, communication exists in most of the organization's activities. Most importantly, communication is a process in which individual, group, and interpersonal activities are coordinated to increase effectiveness through it.

The studies of some of the thinkers of organizational communication in recent years have shown that many of the issues and problems governing the organization have been false to the communication context and regardless of the subtleties of organizational communication, and if managers were aware of these issues, they might be more effective. And they did most of their work. Chester Barnard, in his precious and well-known book, *The Tasks of Managers*, states that the first action of the manager is to develop or develop a communication system. (Mahdavi, et al, 2018, 130)

Organizational communication is the process of exchanging oral, written and nonverbal messages among people who are trying to achieve common goals and perform common tasks. This definition covers the various organizational events. A proper understanding of organizational communication is essential for the efficient and effective implementation of the tasks that employees face. Proper understanding of how organizational texture affects communication can put people in a better position to achieve the goals they have chosen for themselves.

The organization's communicative performance has shaped the thoughts that you can create in others, helping you understand the needs of interacting with you and responding to them (Tabatabaei et al, 2014).

Good communicational performance in the organization leads to improved employee motivation and relies employees on the required information and awareness of the strategies and processes, and helps them understand how to help the organization achieve its goals. (O'Hair, 2002)

Banks and financial institutions are considered as the main organizations providing financial and monetary services and provide essential services to customers, increasing their quality of life. The role of staff in providing services is very important. Given that bank is a financial services organization, the quality and quantity of manpower at the bank is of great importance to customers in providing high quality services. It is necessary to achieve this quality human resource, improve the status of leadership style of managers. Organizations can, by choosing the appropriate leadership style, lead the manpower effectively and efficiently to achieve organizational goals. Therefore, recognizing behavioral patterns of managers (leadership styles) is very important and has a significant impact on the effectiveness of organizational matters (Arab, et al, 2011, 69). Therefore, considering that performance is considered as one of the important components in the analysis of organizations, it is difficult to imagine an organization that is not subject to evaluation and performance measurement. In this research, the researcher seeks to

investigate the relationship the four dimensions of transformational leadership style are related to the communicational performance of the employees of the Samen Al-Hojaj financial and credit institution the northwest Iran branches.

Chart 1 - Analytical model of research

Source: Authors (2019).

METHODS

The present study is based on the purpose of applied research and is descriptive and survey based on data collection. Also, this research is correlational in terms of information analysis method. The statistical population of this research is the staff, managers and deputies of the branches of Samen Al-Hojaj financial and credit Institution in northwestern Iran. Sample size was determined randomly using Cochran formula and 144 samples were obtained. Data collection was done using two transformational leadership and job performance questionnaires:

1.Data on transformational leadership by executives is collected using the Transformational Leadership Questionnaire developed by Bass and Avolio (2004). The questionnaire consists of 20 questions in the form of questions with a scalar scale and four components of Individualized consideration, intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation and idealized influence. Questionnaire questions are based on Likert's five-point scale with options never, seldom, sometimes, often and always. The numerical value of these five options is numbered one to five, with a score of one for never, and a score of five for always. The Transformational Leadership Questionnaire has been used in numerous studies and its validity and reliability have been verified.

2. The second questionnaire was designed by the researcher to collect information about the communicational performance of the staff, which has 12 five-choice questions in accordance with the Likert spectrum. To assess the validity of the questionnaire, the method of using professors 'and experts' opinions was used and to determine its reliability, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used.

Table 1: Number of items and Cronbach's alpha coefficients of the components

	Number of phrases	Cronbach's alpha coefficient
Transformational Leadership Bass and Avolio MLQ Questionnaire	20	0.874
Communicative Performance Questionnaire	12	0.689

Source: Authors (2019).

After completing the questionnaires, the descriptive statistics of the variables were calculated and the graphs and tables were drawn. In the inferential statistics section, SPSS software was used to analyze the data and examine the relationship between variables. To investigate the relationship between employees' communicational performance variable and Individualized consideration, intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation and idealized influence variables, Pearson correlation test was used. Then To study the effect of independent variables of Individualized consideration, intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation and idealized influence on the dependent variable of employee communicational performance Multiple linear regression was used.

RESULTS

In Transformational Leadership Questionnaire, 20 options in the form of the Likert Spectrum have been used. The four dimensions of transformational leadership include intellectual stimulation (phrases 1 through 5), idealized influence (phrases 6 through 12), inspirational motivation (phrases 13 through 16), and Individualized consideration (phrases 17 through 20). In the table below, the average score of each question and the average score of each transformational leadership dimension, which is the mean scores for the terms related to that dimension, is presented. As can be seen, the average score for inspirational motivation is higher than other dimensions and individual considerations lower than other dimensions. Also, in the dimension of intellectual stimulation, the phrase 3 (respectful behavior) has the highest average score and in the dimension of idealized influence, the phrase 10 (taking into account different perspectives and problems for solving problems), in the dimension of inspirational motivation, the phrase 15 (futures) and in the dimension of Individualized consideration, the phrase 20 (help to develop employee abilities) has the highest average score.

In the last row of the table, the final score of the transformative leadership, which is the average score of each questionnaire, is 58.86. This figure represents the moderate quality of transformational leadership in the branches of the Samen Al-Hojaj financial and credit institution in the northwest of the Iran. Because according to the instructions of this questionnaire, the transformational leadership score is between 20 and 100, and the score between 20 and 40

represents the low quality of transformational leadership in the organization, the score between 40 and 60 represents the moderate quality of transformational leadership in the organization and a score above 60 represents high quality of transformational leadership in the organization.

Table 2 - Descriptive statistics of Transformational Leadership Questionnaire Bass and Avolio

Dimensions of Leadership	Phrases	Average score of each Phrase	Average score of dimensions
intellectual stimulation	I feel proud of being in touch with him.	3.14	3.09
	Because of the interest of the group, it overlooks its own interests.	2.42	
	It behaves in such a way as to respect it.	3.60	
	Sense of trust and self-power.	3.57	
	Speaks about his basic beliefs and values.	2.74	
idealized influence	Speaks about the need for a strong sense of purpose.	2.23	2.81
	The ethical and religious implications of decisions are taken into account.	2.71	
	Emphasizes the importance of having a sense of team collaboration about the mission.	3.12	
	Exactly examine the substantive suggestions to ensure that they are appropriate.	2.69	
	When solving problems, consider different perspectives and perspectives.	3.72	
	He wants me to examine problems from different angles.	2.96	
	New ways of thinking suggest how to do it.	2.28	
inspirational motivation	Speaks about an optimistic future.	3.19	3.27
	He speaks with earnestness about what to do.	3.13	
	Emphasizes the importance of futurism.	3.68	
	He hopes that the goals will be achievable.	3.08	
Individualized consideration	Provides guidance and training.	2.68	2.65
	He treats me as a person more than being treated as a member of the group.	2.65	
	He considers me as someone who has the needs of different abilities and creativity.	2.48	
	Helps to develop and develop my abilities.	2.79	
Transformational Leadership Quality Score		58.86	

Source: Authors (2019).

This questionnaire has 12 questions of 5 options in the form of a Likert spectrum. The average score of each question is presented in the table below. According to the table below, the phrase 2 (sympathy with colleagues in Occurrence of a problem) has the highest average compared to other expressions. Also, the mean of employee communicational performance score is 3.77 (scores ranging from 1 to 5), which indicates the average communicational performance of the branch staff of the institute in the northwest of the Iran.

Table 3 - Descriptive statistics of communicational performance questionnaire

Row	Phrases	Average score
1	I have a hearty and constructive relationship with my colleagues.	3.80
2	I sympathize with my colleague in the event of a problem.	4.18
3	I have a respectful and honest relationship with the president and superiors.	3.81
4	I have a sincere and compassionate relationship with customers.	4.09
5	I treat the dissatisfied and angry customers with calmness and patience.	3.85
6	I treat all fair and non-discriminatory clients.	3.67
7	Comments and suggestions from customers are important to me.	3.52
8	I strive to communicate steadily with customers and attract loyal customers.	3.93
9	I am trying to market and attract new customers to the bank.	3.26
10	Positive and hopeful attitude toward myself and others.	3.07
11	Education is effective in communicating better with colleagues and the client.	4.08
12	Adoption and good behavior are influential in customer service and customer engagement.	4.05
Average performance score of employee communication		3.77

Source: Authors (2019).

To investigate the relationship between transformational leadership correlation and its dimensions with communicational performance, Pearson correlation test was used, which the results are presented in the following table.

Table 4 - Pearson Correlation Test between Transformational Leadership and communicational performance

Variables	communicational performance	Description
intellectual stimulation	0.239	99% probability correlation
idealized influence	0.151	no correlation.
inspirational motivation	0.026	no correlation.
Individualized consideration	0.189	95% probability correlation
transformational leadership	0.177	95% probability correlation

Source: Authors (2019).

As shown in the table above, transformational leadership correlates with communicational performance by 95% of probability. Investigating the relationship between leadership dimensions and communicational performance

showed that intellectual stimulation and Individualized consideration have correlate with communication performance. But the dimensions of idealized influence and inspirational motivation with communicational performance do not have a significant correlation.

A multiple regression model has been used to investigate the effect of transformational leadership dimensions on employee's communicational performance. The summary of the model, the results of the analysis of variance and the coefficient table are presented below.

Table 5 - Summary of regression results

R	R2	Adjusted coefficient of determination	Mistake the benchmark
0.689	0.474	0.463	0.084

Source: Authors (2019).

The analysis of variance table shows the significance of regression and the linear relationship between variables of transformational leadership dimensions and employee communicational performance. The level of significance is less than 5% and confirms the case to 99%.

Table 6 - Analysis of variance table

	sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	average of squares	f	The significance level
Regression	13.330	2	6.665	6.639	0.002
left over	141.559	141	1.004		
Total	154.889	143			

Source: Authors (2019).

To Investigate the relative importance of independent variable in determining the communicational performance of employees, the regression coefficients were studied. The values of the regression coefficient table show that the effect of the variable intellectual stimulation on employees' communicational performance is significant at 99%, and the effect of Individualized consideration on employee communicational performance is statistically significant at 95%. For this reason, they enter the regression line equation. Also, the beta weight indicates that the effect of intellectual stimulation on communicational performance is greater than that of Individualized consideration.

Table 8 - Independent variable regression coefficients

Independent variables	The regression coefficient	standard error	Beta weight	T test	Significance level
Constant	3.438	0.347	---	9.918	0.000
intellectual stimulation	0.273	0.086	0.257	3.177	0.002
Individualized consideration	0.189	0.090	0.171	2.112	0.036

Independent variables	Beta factor	t-test	The significance level	Partial regression	Tolerance
Constant	0.035	0.332	0.740	0.028	0.592
intellectual stimulation	0.074	0.886	0.377	0.075	0.935

Source: Authors (2019).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The present research has been carried out to investigate the effect of four dimensions of transformational leadership on communicational performance among employees in the branches of Samen Al-Hojaj financial and credit institute in the northwest of the Iran. To collect data, the transformational leadership questionnaire (MLQ) and communicational performance questionnaire were completed by 144 staff of Samen Al-Hojaj financial and credit institution in the Northwest of Iran. The demographic description of the research samples showed that about 40% of the employees of the institute were between the ages of 25 and 35 years old and about 50% of the employees of the institute were between the ages of 20 and 25 years old, about 85% of them were male and 15% were female. Also, about 80 percent of the staff had graduate and postgraduate degrees.

The results of descriptive statistics questionnaire questions showed that in the MLQ's transformational leadership questionnaire, the average score for inspirational motivation is higher than other aspects and Individualized consideration are lower than other dimensions. In the dimension of intellectual stimulation, respectful behavior, in the dimension of idealized influence, considering different perspectives and perspectives to solve problems, in the dimension of inspirational motivation, prospects and in the aspect of Individualized consideration, assistance in developing the ability of employees had the highest importance from the perspective of the staff of Samen Al-Hojaj financial and credit institution in the north-west branches of Iran.

The final score of transformational leadership is 58.86, which indicates the moderate quality of transformational leadership in the branches of Samen Al-Hojaj financial and credit institution in the northwest of the Iran. In the communicational performance questionnaire, Sympathy with colleagues in the event of a problem, is being paid more attention by the institute staff. Also, the average of the employee's communicational performance score (3.77), indicates the medium average of the communicational performance of the branch staff of the institute.

The results of Pearson correlation test show that there is a meaningful relationship between transformational leadership and communicational performance. The study of the relationship between dimensions of transformational leadership and stable performance has shown that Individualized consideration and intellectual stimulation are correlated with communicational performance. However, the dimensions of idealized influence and inspirational motivation, and communicational performance do not have a significant correlation.

Multiple linear regression analysis was used to investigate the effect of transformational leadership dimensions on the communicational performance of the Institute's employees in the northwest of the Iran. The results showed that the effect of intellectual stimulation on employees' communicational performance is likely to be 99% and the effect of Individualized consideration on employee communicational performance is likely to be 95 Percentage. The effect of intellectual stimulation on communicational performance is also greater than the effect of Individualized consideration.

The results of this study are consistent with some of the results of Shabaninejad et al. (2016) and contradict with some of the results of their study. They studied the relationship between transformational leadership and employee job performance in the Farabi hospital. The results of their study showed that there is a significant relationship between the four components of the transformational leadership style and the job performance of the employees. Also, studying the simultaneous effect of transformational leadership dimensions on job performance using multiple regression showed that 42 percent idealized influence and 39 percent intellectual stimulation had a positive effect on employees' job performance.

Given the importance of an appropriate leadership style for the management of today's organizations, especially organizations whose main mission is to provide services to the people, it is imperative that managers and leaders of these organizations select the appropriate leadership style. Therefore, planning for the implementation of a transformational leadership style as a common style that most researchers and learning organizations should be considered in order to strengthen the organization's performance. Therefore, leaders who avoid interference in important issues and do not have the desire to attend others when they need others to deal with their employees properly, because those leaders do not tend to encounter others and even try to answer immediate and serious questions to their employees.

As a result, employees cannot rely on trust managers. All of these factors undermine employee morale; as a result, organizational performance is actually overwhelmed by the indicator to meet the goals of the organization. One of the subsystems of organizational performance is communicational performance. In this research, we tried to investigate the effect of transformational leadership on the communicational performance of the staff of the institute. Since nongovernmental financial institutions have been proactive in realizing transition-oriented leadership because of their lack of dependence on government finances and part of the private sector. Due to the fact that financial system employees are in direct contact with customers, enhancing their communicational performance will increase the attraction of resources.

Given that in the present research, we sought to identify the effective dimensions of transformational leadership on the worker's communicational performance, we have come to the conclusion that from the four dimensions of the transformational leadership that Bass and Avolio have presented, the Individualized consideration and intellectual stimulation had the most impact on the communicational performance of the staff of the institute. Therefore, it is possible to strengthen the indicators of these dimensions such as mutual respect, strengthening trust, developing staff abilities, respecting the values of the employees, and ... taking more measures to strengthen the employee's communicational performance.

REFERENCES

- Albion, M. J., Gagliardi, R. E. (2007). **A study of transformational leadership, organizational change and job satisfaction.** Retrieved from http://eprints.usq.edu.au/3098/1/Albion_Gagliardi.pdf. USA.
- Amin, I., & Mariani, S. (2017). **PME Learning Model: The Conceptual Theoretical Study Of Metacognition Learning In Mathematics Problem Solving Based On Constructivism.** International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education, 12(3), 333-352. Iran.
- Antonakis, J. (2012). **Transformational and charismatic leadership.** In D. Day & J. Antonakis (Eds.), *The nature of leadership* (pp. 256-288). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications Inc. USA.
- Arab, A., Ahanchian, M. R., Karshaki, H. (2011). **The Role of Leadership Style in Managing Social Entrepreneurship Prediction: A Comparative Study of Governmental Universities with Mashhad Nursing Universities,** Journal of Innovation and Creativity in the Humanities. 3(2): pp. 101-63. Iran.
- Avolio, B. J., Bass, B., Jung, D. I. (1995). **MLQ multifactor leadership questionnaire (Technical Report),** Redwood City, CA, Mind Garden. USA.
- Bass, B. M. (1997). **Does the transactional-transformational leadership paradigm transcend organizational and national boundaries?** American Psychologist, 52(2), pp.130-139. doi: 10.1037/0003-066X.52.2.130. USA.
- Bass, B.M., Avolio, B.J., Jung, D.I., Bers on, Y. (2003). **Predicting unit performance by assessing transformational and transactional leadership.** Journal of Applied Psychology, 88, pp.207-218. USA.
- Bushra, F., Usman, A., Asvir, N. (2011). **Effect of Transformational Leadership on Employees' Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment in Banking Sector of Lahore (Pakistan),** International Journal of Business and Social Science, 2(18): p.261. Iran.
- Cavazotte, F., Moreno, V., Bernardo, J. (2013). **Transformational Leaders and Work Performance: The Mediating Roles of Identification and Self-efficacy,** Bar, 10(4): pp. 490-512. USA.
- Dumdum, U. R., Lowe, K. B., Avolio, B. J. (2002). **A meta-analysis of transformational and transactional leadership correlates of effectiveness and satisfaction: and update and extension.** In B. Avolio & F. Yammarino (Eds.), *Transformational and charismatic leadership: the road ahead* (pp. 35-66). New York: Elsevier Science. USA.

- Judge, T. A., Piccolo, R. F. (2004). ***Transformational and transactional leadership: a meta-analytic test of their relative validity***. Journal of Applied Psychology, 89(5): pp.755-768. doi: 10.1037/0021-9010.89.5.755. USA.
- Legzian, M. Malikzadeh, G. (2011). ***Study of the relationship between readiness for change and the dimensions of the learning organization***. The Prospect of Public Administration, (4): pp.101-118. Iran.
- Lowe, K. B., Gardner, W. L. (2000). ***Ten years of leadership quarterly: contributions and challenges for the future***. The Leadership Quarterly, 11(4): pp. 459-514. doi: 10.1016/S1048-9843(00)00059-X. USA.
- Mahdavi, S. S., et al. (2018). ***The role of communication skills of managers in business development with emphasis on customer orientation***, Social Development Studies of Iran, 10(2): 127-152. Iran.
- Mirkamali, S. M., Zahedi, S. (2012). ***Investigating the Role of Explanation of the Burke-Litwin Organizational Change Model on Organizational Performance; Case Study: Alzakra University***. The Perspective of Public Administration, pp.31-53. Iran.
- Nezhad, N. J., & Jenaabadi, H. (2014). ***Studying Effect of Communication Skills and Leadership Styles of Manager on Knowledge Management of Zahedan University of Medical Sciences, Iran***. Iran.
- Nordin, N. (2011). ***The Influence of Emotional intelligence, Leadership Behavior and Organizational Commitment on Organizational Readiness for Change in Higher Learning Institution***. Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences, (29): 129-138. Iran.
- O'Hair, D., Friedrich, G. W., Dixon, L. D. (2002). ***Strategic communication in Business and the profession***, Boston: Houghton Mifflin Co. USA.
- Tabatabaei, F., Karahrudi, M. M., & Bagheri, M. (2014). ***Monitoring and zoning sultry phenomena in the southern provinces of Iran***. UCT. J. Soc. Sci. Human. Res, 1-8. Iran.
- Teal, T. (1998). ***The human side of management***. In Harvard Business School Press (Org.), Harvard business review: on leadership, Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press, (pp. 147-169). USA.
- Timothy C. O., et al. (2011). ***Effect of Leadership Style on Organizational Performance: A Survey of Selected Small-Scale Enterprises in Ikosi-Ketu Council Development Area of Lagos State, Nigeria***. Australian Journal of Business and Management Research, 1(7): pp. 99-110. USA.
- Zahedi, Sh. Mortazavi, L. (2010). ***Explaining the role of the interface between emotional conflict between commitment to change and the process factor of changing the regional power company in Khorasan***. The Moderator of Humanities in Management Researches in Iran, 14 (3): pp.121-143. Iran.